

Annex 4: Bio4HUMAN's solution infosheets

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Bio4HUMAN - Identifying bio-based solutions for waste management applicable to the humanitarian sector

Bio-Based Solution Info Sheet

MYCELIUM PROTECTIVE MATERIAL

Baseline alternative

Plastic filling in parcels.

General description

Eco-friendly packaging solutions combining cardboard and natural shock-absorbing pads made from mycelium. It uses paper capsules filled with safepads to protect products during transport.

- 100% natural, bio-based composite made from mycelium (the root system of fungi) and agricultural or wood waste like sawdust or hemp shavings.
- Mycelium acts as a natural binder, replacing plastic foams in packaging.
- The technology allows for efficient, low-cost production and can be easily adapted to places like Africa because it grows fast on agricultural waste, requires minimum energy and equipment, builds itself into usable shapes, and is scalable and clean.

Lifespan

Reusable, like the conventional product.

Environmental aspects - added value

- End of life: 100% biodegradable (45 days in soil/compost, 180 days in water, 1-3 years outdoors).
- Do not use primary raw materials, but waste that has no further use except for palletization and incineration.

Additional comments

- Examples of implementation: packaging for construction products; edge and corner protection for packaged goods.
- The packaging system has already been used in transportation to African locations.

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monta biopack® SELF-ADHESIVE TAPE

Baseline alternative

Conventional plastic tape.

General description

Certified sustainable self-adhesive tape made from 90% renewable resources, its carrier is a bio-based PLA film that is coated with a natural rubber adhesive.

Applicable for:

- Sealing biodegradable bags and films and other sustainable packaging types;
- Permanent closure of medium heavy to heavy cardboard boxes;
- Suitable for manual application in various hand- and table dispensers as well as in automated packaging machines;
- Bundling garden waste.

Lifespan

Single-use product. This product is a component of tertiary packaging and is used to secure the load; once the packaging is unpacked, the tape is discarded.

Cost

Depends on the number of units purchased, but usually between 1.786-1.875 EUR VS baseline: 0.50-1.50 EUR.

Environmental aspects - added value

- End of life: Under industrial composting conditions, this packaging tape biodegrades within a few months. It has a compostability certificate.
- Made from renewable raw materials, reducing fossil plastic dependency.
- Proven sustainability - certified conformity with “OK COMPOST INDUSTRIAL” scheme by TÜV Austria.

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METALLISED BARRIER LAYER FOR FOOD CONTACT APPLICATIONS - TONGLI PACKAGING

Baseline alternative

Metallized sachets for food.

General description

- This solution is made from PLA, cellulose metallized and cellophane.
- It can be used to contain Ready-to-Use Therapeutic food (RUTF).
- High barriers to moisture, sunlight, and oxygen.

Lifespan

Single-use product. Same lifespan as that of the conventional product (2 years).

Cost

0.047 EUR per unit VS baseline: 150 sachets for 50.40 EUR (0.33 EUR per sachet).

Environmental aspects - added value

End of life: 100% biodegradable and home-compostable in natural conditions.

Additional comments

- The data are estimates because these products are not currently manufactured with these dimensions.
- Usually beneficiaries bring empty pouches back to a health facility.

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MONOFILAMENT FISHING/MOSQUITO NETS

Baseline alternative

Conventional monofilament fishing nets made from fossil-based plastics (e.g. nylon, polypropylene) / conventional mosquito nets.

General description

Biobased and biodegradable bioplastic formulations for monofilament fishing nets. These nets are engineered to perform like conventional plastic nets but degrade naturally in marine or soil environments, reducing their long-term environmental impact.

Lifespan

Comparable to the conventional alternative (1-2 years).

Environmental aspects - added value

- End of life: Under industrial composting conditions, this packaging tape biodegrades within a few months.
- The correct disposal for the biodegradable nets is to reuse them as much as possible, recycle them if possible, and discard in an industrial compost where the material will be biologically recycled.
- Made of bio-based polymers (PLA – maize), reducing reliance on fossil resources.
- Marine-degradable, helping to mitigate ghost net and plastic waste problems. The nets will not dissolve in fresh water.
- Mosquito nets: impregnation with insect repellents should not affect biodegradability.

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DISPOSABLE BAG FROM RENEWABLE RESOURCES

Baseline alternative

Conventional plastic bags made from fossil-based polymers.

General description

- Biodegradable and compostable bags made from renewable resources.
- Already market-ready and part of Bio4Pack's commercial product line.
- Size range: 8L, 10L, 30L, 60L, 120L, 240L.

Lifespan

Single-use product.

Environmental aspects - added value

End of life: fully industrially compostable.

Additional comments

- Made from renewable raw materials, reducing fossil plastic dependency.
- Reduces microplastic pollution and landfill waste.
- Can be used for waste disposal.

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L'AMON BIODEGRADABLE LAMINATING FILM

Baseline alternative

Conventional plastic laminating film.

General description

LAM'ON is a 100% biodegradable laminating film for print and packaging. It is derived from renewable resources like corn. The glue layer that was developed specifically for the needs of the industry is completely toxic-free. It is also water soluble and that will ease the recycling process.

Main characteristics of LAM'ON:

- Crafted from bio-based materials (85%).
- Compostable (100%).
- 90 cm width, 50 µm max thickness.
- Applied on standard laminators.
- Printable
- Water resistant to keep the products safe without compromising on sustainability.

Lifespan

6 months. Single-use product: the film is used for bundling or transporting (it is a transport packaging); once used, it is discarded.

Cost

It depends on order. The price is usually between 6 and 8 euros per kilogram.

Cost of the conventional product: It depends on the thickness and the supplier, but it is usually approximately between 2 and 5 euros per kilogram.

Environmental aspects - added value

End of life: 100% industrially compostable, certified to EN 13432 standards. In industrial composting conditions, the film breaks down into carbon dioxide and water in under 12 weeks, leaving no microplastics or toxic residues behind.

Additional comments

- It is the conscious choice for bio-based and compostable thermal laminating films for paper and cardboard application and packaging foils for garments, cosmetics and food.
- Must be stored in under 30°C in order to minimize the deterioration of the film properties in general.

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BLACK SOLDIER FLIES (BSF)

Baseline alternative

Traditional waste management methods.

General description

The Black Soldier Fly (BSF) helps turn organic waste into high-protein and fat-rich animal feed for livestock, fish, and pets. Its larvae eat the waste, reducing it by 50–80%, and can be harvested after about 14 days. Up to 20% of the waste is converted into useful biomass. The larvae are processed into feed, and the leftover material (frass) can be used as compost or soil conditioner.

A BSF facility includes steps like waste preparation, feeding larvae, separating them from residue, and turning both into useful products.

Cost

Smallest units start at a few hundred EUR .

Environmental aspects - added value

- **Waste Reduction:** BSF larvae consume large amounts of organic waste, significantly reducing waste volume by 50–80% and easing pressure on landfills.
- **Lower GHG Emissions:** BSF farming produces far fewer greenhouse gases than traditional livestock and minimizes emissions from waste transport and decomposition.
- **BSF production** requires little land and water, making it ideal for space- and resource-constrained settings.
- The leftover frass can be used as an organic fertilizer, improving soil health, and reducing reliance on chemical inputs.
- **Fishmeal Alternative:** BSF protein replaces fishmeal in animal feed, helping reduce overfishing and protect marine biodiversity.

Additional comments

- BSF larvae require a warm, stable climate and thrive in temperatures between 24 and 30°C. Consistent humidity is also crucial, with optimal levels above 60%.
- The technology is already widespread across the African continent – present in Ghana, Namibia, Mozambique, South Africa, Uganda, Ethiopia, Ivory Coast and Botswana.

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SANITARY PADS

Baseline alternative

Traditional non-compostable cotton sanitary pads

General description

Anandi Eco+ pads use no harmful chemicals and break down into manure after use, helping the environment and recycling resources.

- These affordable pads are produced and sold by local entrepreneurs in areas where sanitary pads are hard to get.
- They use natural, low-cost materials from locally available agriculture like jute, banana fiber, and plant waste to keep prices low.
- Each pad is made in a small factory run and staffed by local women. This creates jobs and helps women learn business and marketing skills. The factories use simple technology that makes high-quality, comfortable pads at low cost.

Lifespan

6 months. Single-use product: the film is used for bundling or transporting (it is a transport packaging); once used, it is discarded.

Cost

30 pads at 6 USD.

Environmental aspects - added value

End of life: 100% home compostable. In a compost environment, at least 90% of the pad are biodegraded within 90-180 days. The pads can be disposed easily in the backyard mud pit of any rural household to avoid polluting the environment and create bio-manure for agriculture.

Additional comments

- Free of harsh chemicals, fragrances & plastics.
- Each mini factory is easy to operate and maintain. With basic training, women can produce superior quality Anandi pads and eventually manage their own factories.
- The Mini-Factories require minimal electricity to operate and have a built-in quality standard.
- Operating for 8-10 hours per day, one mini-factory can provide a hygienic menstrual management option for 200,000+ women each month.

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GS - GREEN PLA BOTTLE

Baseline alternative

Conventional plastic bottles.

General description

PLA (Polylactic Acid) bottles are made entirely from plants, including the cap and label. Unlike regular plastic, they come from renewable sources and are better for the environment.

Sizes from 100 ml up to 2L. Currently, 250 ml, 500 ml, and 1-liter bottles are ready for production. They meet international standards and can be made with different neck sizes (28 mm and 38 mm). They can be used for water or oil.

Lifespan

9-12 months.

Cost

0.6-0.7 EUR/bottle (1-2L) VS baseline: 1L: between 0.4-0.8 EUR; 2L: between 0.7-1.2 EUR, depending on the brand.

Environmental aspects - added value

- End of life: Industrially compostable. In nature/landfill the bottle will take a long time to break down – several years.
- When they break down in nature or industrial compost, they do not create toxins or microplastic.
- Recyclable and can be burned releasing no harmful toxins, offering multiple end-of-life disposal options that are less harmful to the environment. Whether the bottles are recycled, composted, or used for energy recovery, their plant-based nature guarantees minimal environmental impact.
- 100% plant-based and 100% non-GMO.

Additional comments

- For the product itself it is TRL 9 (full commercial deployment) - it means the possibility to produce blown PLA bottles, PLA bottles with water and PLA preforms and biobased caps. As for the production (bottling) unit – the Solution Owner is at stage 4 (technology validated in a lab).
- The data are estimates because these products are not currently manufactured with these dimensions.
- Better to not expose directly to sun as it starts to deform at 60°C-65°C.

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DIGESTER TECHNOLOGIES (BIOGAS)

Baseline alternative

Traditional waste management.

General description

A biogas digester is an airtight container that facilitates the anaerobic digestion of organic waste to produce biogas, a renewable energy source. It's a sustainable method for waste management, converting materials like animal manure, food scraps, and agricultural residues into usable energy.

As this waste decomposes, it produces a gas called biogas, which is a mix of methane and carbon dioxide.

- This gas can be burned to cook food, heat homes, or generate electricity.
- What's left behind in the tank is called digestate. The digestate is always composed of 2 fractions: solid and liquid. The solid fraction can be composted or used as an enhancer in composting process. The liquid fraction can be used directly or after a stabilization.
- The process is sustainable, reduces odours, and turns waste into useful energy and nutrients.
- It's especially helpful in rural or off-grid areas, where it can reduce reliance on firewood or fossil fuels.
- Biogas digesters work best with a steady input of organic material and stable temperatures — usually warmer climates are ideal.

Cost

The price is indicative and depend on the type of technology, size and material use to build the biogas system.

Initial construction and installation costs: 5000 €.Ongoing/recurring annual costs: 300 €

Environmental aspects - added value

- Reduces greenhouse gas emissions by capturing methane that would otherwise escape from decomposing waste on landfills.
- Decreases reliance on fossil fuels by providing a renewable source of energy
- Prevents pollution by safely treating organic waste, reducing runoff into soil and water bodies.
- Produces organic fertilizer, which improves soil health and reduces the need for chemical alternatives.

Additional comments

- Can be integrated into a fully closed-loop system for the sustainable management of some types of waste at a very localised level.
- Can be designed at different scale levels. Perhaps some basic training on the setup and maintenance is needed
- Safety considerations: Hygienic issues when dealing with waste and digestate, especially with manure and human waste; Safety signs, locks, logbooks and gas alarms are required.

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